

Abstract

A matched asymptotic structure is constructed to incorporate acoustic flows in symmetric passages of diminishing and of fixed widths, as the Reynolds number grows indefinitely. The structure is constructed in the d^*-y^* plane, where d^* is the half width and y^* is the cross coordinate normal to the axis of symmetry. Identified are three distinct regions I, II and III that are characterized by different physical processes. In region II, the core of the fixed width channel, the flow is essentially inviscid. In region III, close to the boundary of the fixed width channel, the flow is viscous of boundary layer type with prescribed pressure gradient. In region I, the diminishing width channel, the flow is viscous with non-prescribed pressure gradient. Matching is performed to close the leading order perturbation problems, and is shown to be mandatory.

1. Introduction

Synthesized voices based on models devoid of viscous losses do not sound natural. Inclusion of viscous losses would, hopefully, remedy this. One approach is to involve viscous boundary layers [1,2]. This, however, corresponds to passages of widths that allow for dominant inviscid core and peripheral boundary layers. Smaller width passages were treated by Wilhelms-Tricarico and McGowan [3]. Their concise presentation needs elaboration. This is the endeavor undertaken in this article. An asymptotic analysis of the full two-dimensional problem is performed. In the main text, we handle the case of a channel and, in Appendix A, we present the corresponding results for a circular pipe. In Appendix B, we numerically exhibit the tendency to boundary layer formation, as the passage width increases.

2. Flow Configuration

We are concerned with the flow of a perfect gas (of specific heat at constant pressure c_p^* and ratio of specific heats γ) through a straight channel (of length ℓ^* and width $2d^*$) whose walls are thermally insulated. Due to symmetry, the study is performed on one half of the channel only. Figure 1 shows the geometry and coordinate axes (x^* , y^*) along and normal to the axis of symmetry, as well as the corresponding velocity components (u^* , v^*). Initially, at $t^* = 0$, the gas is at rest having temperature θ_0^* , pressure p_0^* , thermal conductivity k_0^* , and viscosity μ_0^* . Subsequently, at the inlet $x^* = 0$, a time varying pressure $\hat{p}^*(t^*, y^*; d^*)$ with pressure gradient $\hat{p}_{x^*}^*(t^*, y^*; d^*)$ is applied.

Fig. 1: Flow configuration.

3. Dimensional Problem

With asterisks dropped, for convenience, the flow is governed by the following equations, where a subscript denotes differentiation.

$\rho_t + (\rho u)_x + (\rho v)_y = 0$	(1C)
$\rho(u_t + uu_x + vu_y) + p_x = [\mu(u_y + v_x)]_y + 2[\mu u_x]_x + [\lambda\mu(u_x + v_y)]_x$	(1L)
$\rho(v_t + uv_x + vv_y) + p_y = [\mu(u_y + v_x)]_x + 2[\mu v_y]_y + [\lambda\mu(u_x + v_y)]_y$	(1N)
$\rho c_p(\theta_t + u\theta_x + v\theta_y) - (p_t + up_x + vp_y)$ $= (k\theta_x)_x + (k\theta_y)_y + \mu[2u_x^2 + 2v_y^2 + (u_y + v_x)^2 + \lambda(u_x + v_y)^2]$	(1E)
$\theta = \frac{\gamma}{(\gamma - 1)c_p} \frac{p}{\rho}$	(1S)
$\frac{\mu}{\mu_0} = \frac{k}{k_0} = f\left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0}\right), f(1) = 1, f'(1) = \beta$	(1μ)

where λ is the viscosity ratio. For a linear viscosity/temperature relation, $f(z) = z$ and $\beta = 1$.

The boundary and initial conditions are

$y = 0: u_y = 0, v = 0, \theta_y = 0$	(1Aa-c)
$y = d: u = 0, v = 0, \theta_y = 0;$	(1Ad-f)
$x = 0: p = p_0 + \hat{p}(t, y; d), p_x = \hat{p}_x(t, y; d)$	(1Ag,h)
$t = 0: u = 0, v = 0, \rho = \rho_0, p = p_0, \theta = \theta_0, \mu = \mu_0$	(1Ai-n)

4. Nondimensionalization

Define the characteristic temperature, velocity (speed of sound), and time

$$\theta_0^* = \frac{\gamma}{(\gamma - 1)c_p^*} \frac{p_0^*}{\rho_0^*}, c_0^* = \left(\frac{\gamma p_0^*}{\rho_0^*}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, t_0^* = \frac{l^*}{c_0^*}$$

and introduce thermal conductivity, viscosity and width parameters

$$\sigma = \frac{k_0^*}{\mu_0^* c_p^*}, \nu = \frac{\mu_0^*}{\rho_0^* c_0^* l^*} = \varepsilon^2, d = \frac{d^*}{l^*}$$

and nondimensional variables

$$t = t^*/t_0^*, (x, y, \ell) = (x^*, y^*, \ell^*)/l^*, (u, v) = (u^*, v^*)/c_0^*$$

$$\rho = \rho^*/\rho_0^*, p = p^*/p_0^*, \theta = \theta^*/\theta_0^*, \mu = \mu^*/\mu_0^*$$

where l^* is a suitably choose characteristic length. If we choose $l^* = \ell^*$, then $\ell = 1$. Another choice, when the inlet conditions represent a wave, is a specified number of wave lengths.

The nondimensional equations are

$\rho_t + (\rho u)_x + (\rho v)_y = 0$	(2C)
$\rho(u_t + uu_x + vv_y) + \frac{1}{\gamma} p_x = \varepsilon^2 \langle [\mu(u_y + v_x)]_y + 2[\mu u_x]_x + [\lambda \mu(u_x + v_y)]_x \rangle$	(2L)
$\rho(v_t + uv_x + vv_y) + \frac{1}{\gamma} p_y = \varepsilon^2 \langle [\mu(u_y + v_x)]_x + 2[\mu v_y]_y + [\lambda \mu(u_x + v_y)]_y \rangle$	(2N)
$\rho_t + u\rho_x + v\rho_y - \frac{\rho}{\gamma p} (p_t + up_x + vp_y)$ $= -\varepsilon^2 \left\langle \frac{1}{\sigma} \left\{ \left[\mu \left(\frac{p}{\rho} \right)_x \right]_x + \left[\mu \left(\frac{p}{\rho} \right)_y \right]_y \right\} + (\gamma - 1) \mu [2u_x^2 + 2v_y^2 + (u_y + v_x)^2 + \lambda(u_x + v_y)^2] \right\rangle \frac{\rho}{p}$	(2E)
$\theta = \frac{p}{\rho}$	(2S)
$\mu = f(\theta), f(1) = 1, f'(1) = \beta$	(2μ)

Note that, in the energy equation (1E), θ has been dispensed with in favor of ρ , using the equation of state (1S).

The nondimensional conditions are

$y = 0: u_y = 0, v = 0, \theta_y = 0$	(2Aa-c)
$y = d: u = 0, v = 0, \theta_y = 0$	(2Ad-f)
$x = 0: p = \hat{p}(t, y; d), p_x = \hat{p}_x(t, y; d)$	(2Ag,h)
$t = 0: u = 0, v = 0, \rho = 1, p = 1, \theta = 1, \mu = 1$	(2Ai-n)

5. Asymptotic Analysis

We perform matched asymptotic perturbation analysis as $\varepsilon \sim 0$. This corresponds to small viscosity and diminishing inlet triggering disturbances, expressed by $\hat{p} = 1 + \varepsilon \gamma q(t, y; d)$ and $\hat{p}_x = \varepsilon \gamma g(t, y; d)$.

Fig. 2: Asymptotic regions and scalings. (a) d - y plane (b) d - z plane

6. Asymptotic structure

The asymptotic structure that incorporates the acoustic flow in both diminishing and fixed width channels, as the viscosity vanishes, is better established in the d - y plane of Fig. 2a, and in the d - z plane of Fig. 2b, where $z = d - y$. We identify three distinct regions I, II and III occupying the sector lying between $y = 0$ and $y = d$, or between $z = 0$ and $z = d$. These regions are characterized by different physical processes. In region I, the core of the fixed width channel, the flow is essentially inviscid. In region II, close to the boundary of the fixed width channel, the flow is viscous of boundary layer type with prescribed pressure gradient. In region III, the diminishing width channel, the flow is viscous with non-prescribed pressure gradient.

7. Asymptotic expansions

The flow variables expand as follows, in all three regions:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho &= 1 + \varepsilon\rho_1 + \varepsilon^2\rho_2 + \dots, p = 1 + \varepsilon\gamma p_1 + \varepsilon^2\gamma p_2 + \dots \\ \theta &= 1 + \varepsilon\theta_1 + \dots, \mu = 1 + \varepsilon\mu_1 + \dots \\ u &= \varepsilon u_1 + \varepsilon^2 u_2 + \dots, v = \varepsilon^2 v_1 + \varepsilon^3 v_2 + \dots \\ q &= q_1 + \varepsilon q_2 \dots, g = g_1 + \varepsilon g_2 \dots\end{aligned}$$

As usual, the above expansions are introduced into Problem (2), in the concerned region, to arrive at problems governing the successive orders of approximation, there. Matching closes the problems; identifying any unknowns. As a convention, a superscript identifies the concerned region. When no confusion is expected, the superscripts are dropped, for convenience.

In Region I [$d = O(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon D$, $y = O(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon Y$], Eq. (2N) gives $p_{1Y}^I = 0$ and $p_{2Y}^I = 0$ showing that p_1^I and p_2^I are independent of Y and, consequently, so should be p_{1x}^I and p_{2x}^I . In particular, the leading order triggering perturbations, at $x = 0$, q_1^I and g_1^I are independent of Y . Use of $p_{1Y}^I = 0$ in Eq. (2S) results in $\theta_{1Y}^I = -\rho_{1Y}^I$; leading to the boundary conditions $\rho_{1Y}^I = 0$ at $Y = 0$, and $Y = D$.

Likewise, in Region II [$d = O(1)$, $y = O(1)$], p_1^{II} , q_1^{II} and g_1^{II} are independent of y and $\rho_{1y}^{II} = 0$ at $y = d$, and in Region III [$d = O(1)$, $z = O(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon Z$], p_1^{III} , q_1^{III} and g_1^{III} are independent of Z and $\rho_{1Z}^{III} = 0$ at $Z = 0$.

8. Region I

The problem governing the leading order perturbations ρ_1 , u_1 , v_1 and p_1 are

$\rho_{1t} + u_{1x} + v_{1Y} = 0$	(3C)
$u_{1t} + p_{1x} = u_{1YY}$	(3L)
$\rho_{1t} - p_{1t} = \sigma^{-1}\rho_{1YY}$	(3E)
$Y = 0: u_{1Y} = 0, v_1 = 0, \rho_{1Y} = 0$ $Y = D: u_1 = 0, v_1 = 0, \rho_{1Y} = 0$ $x = 0: p_1 = q_1(t; D), p_{1x} = g_1(t; D)$ $t = 0: u_1 = 0, v_1 = 0, \rho_1 = 0, p_1 = 0$	(3A)

Average (3C) and (3E) over Y , to get, where an overbar denotes an average,

$\bar{\rho}_{1t} + \bar{u}_{1x} = 0$	(3C)
$\bar{\rho}_{1t} - p_{1t} = 0$	(3E)

which combine to give

$p_{1t} + \bar{u}_{1x} = 0$	(3CE)
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Applying the Laplace transform

$$F(s) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t)e^{-st} dt$$

we get

$sR_1 + U_{1x} + V_{1Y} = 0$	(4C)
$sU_1 + P_{1x} = U_{1YY}$	(4L)
$sR_1 - sP_1 = \sigma^{-1}R_{1YY}$	(4E)
$sP_1 + \bar{U}_{1x} = 0$	(4CE)
$Y = 0: U_{1Y} = 0, V_1 = 0, R_{1Y} = 0$ $Y = D: U_1 = 0, V_1 = 0, R_{1Y} = 0$ $x = 0: P_1 = Q_1(s; D), P_{1x} = G_1(s; D)$	(4A)

Equation (4E) for R_1 together with the boundary conditions on R_1 at $Y = 0$ and $Y = D$ has the solution

$R_1 = P_1$	(5R)
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Thus, ρ_1 is independent of Y .

Equation (4L) for U_1 together with the boundary conditions on U_1 at $Y = 0$ and at $Y = D$ has the solution

$U_1 = -\frac{1}{s} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)} \right] P_{1x}$	(5U)
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Equation (5U) is true at $x = 0$, which means that U_1 is Y -dependent, there.

Averaging U_1 over Y , gives

$\bar{U}_1 = -\frac{B^2}{s} P_{1x}$	(5U)
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where,

$$B = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\tanh(\sqrt{s}D)}{\sqrt{s}D}} < 1 \quad (5B)$$

Differentiation of Eq. (5U), with respect to x , and use of Eq. (4CE), give as equation for P_1 ,

$$B^2 P_{1xx} - s^2 P_1 = 0 \quad (5P)$$

Differentiation of Eq. (5U), with respect to x , and use of Eq. (5P), give

$$U_{1x} = -\frac{s}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)} \right] P_1 \quad (5U_x)$$

Substituting (5R) and (5U_x) into (4C) and integrating over the interval $[0, Y]$, we get

$$V_1 = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{B^2} \tanh(\sqrt{s}D) \left[\frac{Y}{D} - \frac{\sinh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\sinh(\sqrt{s}D)} \right] P_1 \quad (6V)$$

Note that the conditions $V_1 = 0$ at $Y = 0$ and at $Y = D$ are satisfied.

The solution of Eq. (5P), satisfying the boundary conditions at $x = 0$: $P_1 = Q_1$ and $P_{1x} = G_1$, is

$$P_1 = Q_1 \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1 \frac{B}{s} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) \quad (6P)$$

with the derivative

$$P_{1x} = Q_1 \frac{s}{B} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1 \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) \quad (6P_x)$$

Leaving Region I to Region II or Region III,

$$B \sim 1 - \varepsilon \frac{1}{2\sqrt{s}d} + \dots \quad (7B)$$

Leaving Region I to Region II,

$$P_1^I \sim \lim_{D \rightarrow d/\varepsilon} Q_1^I \cdot \cosh(sx) + \lim_{D \rightarrow d/\varepsilon} G_1^I \cdot \frac{1}{s} \sinh(sx) = \tilde{P}_1^I \quad (7P)$$

$$U_1^I \sim -\frac{1}{s} \tilde{P}_{1x}^I \quad (7U)$$

$$V_1^I \sim \sqrt{s} \frac{y}{d} \tilde{P}_1^I \quad (7V)$$

Both limiting U_1^I and V_1^I satisfy the boundary conditions at $y = 0$.

Leaving Region I to Region III,

$P_1^I \sim \tilde{P}_1^I$	(8P)
$U_1^I \sim -\frac{1}{s}(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z})\tilde{P}_{1x}^I$	(8U)
$V_1^I \sim \sqrt{s}(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z})\tilde{P}_1^I$	(8V)

Both limiting U_1^I and V_1^I satisfy the boundary conditions at $Z = 0$.

9. Region II

The problem governing ρ_1 , u_1 , v_1 and p_1 is

$\rho_{1t} + u_{1x} = 0$	(9C)
$u_{1t} + p_{1x} = 0$	(9L)
$\rho_{1t} - p_{1t} = 0$	(9E)
$y = 0: u_{1y} = 0, \rho_{1y} = 0$ $x = 0: p_1 = q_1(t; d), p_{1x} = g_1(t; d)$ $t = 0: u_1 = 0, \rho_1 = 0, p_1 = 0$	(9A)

Using the initial conditions at $t = 0$, Eq. (9E) integrates to $\rho_1 = p_1$.

Applying the Laplace transformation, we get

$sR_1 + U_{1x} = 0$	(10C)
$sU_1 + P_{1x} = 0$	(10L)
$R_1 = P_1$	(10R)

They combine to give

$$P_{1xx} - s^2 P_1 = 0$$

with the solution

$P_1 = Q_1 \cosh(sx) + G_1 \frac{1}{s} \sinh(sx)$	(10P)
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Then Eq. (10L) rewrites

$U_1 = -\frac{1}{s}P_{1x}$	(10U)
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Both equations, together with Eq. (10R), guarantee the satisfaction of $U_{1y} = 0$ and $R_{1y} = 0$ at $y = 0$.

10. Region III

The equations governing ρ_1 , u_1 , v_1 and p_1 are

$\rho_{1t} + u_{1x} - v_{1z} = 0$	(11C)
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$u_{1t} + p_{1x} = u_{1zz}$	(11L)
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$\rho_{1t} - p_{1t} = \frac{1}{\sigma}\rho_{1zz}$	(11E)
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with the Laplace transforms

$sR_1 + U_{1x} - V_{1z} = 0$	(12C)
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$sU_1 + P_{1x} = U_{1zz}$	(12L)
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$sR_1 - sP_1 = \frac{1}{\sigma}R_{1zz}$	(12E)
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where, due to matching with Region II, Region III has the prescribed pressure

$P_1 = P_1^{II}$	(12P)
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which means $Q_1^{III} = Q_1^{II}$ and $G_1^{III} = G_1^{II}$.

Equations (12L) and (12E) have, as solutions satisfying the conditions at $Z = 0$ ($y = d$) and the matching conditions to Region II as $Z \sim \infty$

$U_1 = -\frac{1}{s}(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z})P_{1x}^{II}$	(12U)
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$R_1 = P_1^{II}$	(12R)
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Finally, Eq. (12C) integrates to

$V_1 = \sqrt{s}(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z})P_1^{II}$	(12V)
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It has been shown that, in all three regions, $\rho_1 = p_1$. Then, Eq. (2S) gives $\theta_1 = (\gamma - 1)p_1$, and Eq. (2μ) gives $\mu_1 = \beta(\gamma - 1)p_1$.

11. Matching

Matching of Regions II and III to Region I is possible provided that

$\lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} Q_1^{II} = \lim_{D \rightarrow d/\varepsilon} Q_1^I$	(13Q)
$\lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} G_1^{II} = \lim_{D \rightarrow d/\varepsilon} G_1^I$	(13G)

which implies

$\lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} P_1^{II} = \tilde{P}_1^I = \lim_{D \rightarrow d/\varepsilon} P_1^I$	(13P)
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12. Composite expressions

The following additive composite expressions are constructed.

$R_1 = P_1 = Q_1^I \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \frac{B}{s} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right)$ $+ (Q_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} Q_1^{II}) \cosh(sx) + (G_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} G_1^{II}) \frac{1}{s} \sinh(sx)$	(14P)
$P_{1x} = \left[Q_1^I \frac{s}{B} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) \right]$ $+ [(Q_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} Q_1^{II})s \sinh(sx) + (G_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} G_1^{II}) \cosh(sx)]$	(14P _x)
$U_1 = -\left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)}\right] \left[Q_1^I \frac{1}{B} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \frac{1}{s} \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) \right]$ $-(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z}) [(Q_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} Q_1^{II}) \sinh(sx) + (G_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} G_1^{II}) \frac{1}{s} \cosh(sx)]$	(14U)
$U_{1x} = -\frac{s}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)} \right] \left[Q_1^I \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \frac{B}{s} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) \right]$ $-s(1 - e^{-\sqrt{s}Z}) [(Q_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} Q_1^{II}) \cosh(sx) + (G_1^{II} - \lim_{d \rightarrow \varepsilon D} G_1^{II}) \frac{1}{s} \sinh(sx)]$	(14U _x)

By setting $x = \ell$, we arrive at the exit conditions.

13. Special case

In case of the independence of the inlet pressure and pressure gradient q and g of the channel width d ,

$R_1 = P_1 = Q_1^I \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \frac{B}{s} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) = P_1^I$	(15P)
$P_{1x} = Q_1^I \frac{s}{B} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) + G_1^I \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B}x\right) = P_{1x}^I$	(15P _x)
$U_1 = -\frac{1}{s} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)}\right] P_{1x}^I$	(15U)
$U_{1x} = -\frac{s}{B^2} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}Y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{s}D)}\right] P_1^I$	(15U _x)

In this case, the solution in the diminishing channel generates those in the finite channel, in a regular fashion. Matching would seem unnecessary; however, matching cannot be avoided, for, according to Eq. (7V), V_1^{II} would be dependent on y . But, in Region II, $v_{1t} + p_{2y} = 0$ which transforms to $sV_1^{II} + P_{2y}^{II} = 0$. Integration, then, shows that P_2^{II} is dependent on y . It cannot be generated, in a regular fashion, from P_2^I , which is independent of y .

14. Conclusion

Lighthill [1] treated the one-dimensional boundary layer flow in a passage assuming: spatially uniform pressure gradient, negligible changes in density and viscosity, and zero cross-flow velocities. The balance of forces in the boundary layer led to a dimensional form of the momentum equation (11L). Following Lighthill, Wilhelms-Tricarico and McGowan [3] applied the boundary layer momentum equation (11L) to the full flow in a small passage. The current analysis incorporates the works of [1] and [3].

An elaborate two-dimensional matched asymptotic analysis is performed on the acoustic flow, initiated from silence conditions, through a symmetric passage. The asymptotic structure incorporates both passages of finite and of diminishing width. The asymptotic orders of leading perturbations are revealed. The independence of the leading pressure perturbation of the cross coordinate is established. The carry over of the boundary layer momentum equation (11L) for a passage of finite width to the full flow in a passage of diminishing width is proven justified. The variation of the leading density, temperature and viscosity perturbations are found to be in accord with that of the pressure perturbation. The contribution of the cross velocity, which is absent in [1] and [3], is taken into account.

References

- [1] J. Lighthill, *Waves in Fluids*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1978.
- [2] A. Mohsen, T. El-Mistikawy and M. Hesham, Acoustic model of the vocal tract with boundary layer corrections, Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Minneapolis, MN, USA, 1993. DOI: 10.1109/ICASSP.1993.319364.
- [3] R. Wilhelms-Tricarico and R. S. McGowan, Rational approximations of viscous losses in vocal tract acoustic modeling, J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 115 (6), 3195-3201. DOI: 10.1121/1.1738686.

Appendix A

Here, we account for the case of the acoustic flow in a circular pipe. Figure 1, now, depicts half of a meridional plane with y and d being the radial distance and the radius, respectively. The analysis proceeds in the same way as in the case of the channel presented, in details, in the main text. The two cases are in total agreement as far as Regions II and III are concerned. The difference is in the solution in Region I. For the pipe, the governing equations of the first perturbations are, maintaining the same equation numbers,

$\frac{\partial \rho_1}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{Y} \frac{\partial Y v_1}{\partial Y} = 0$	(3C)
$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial p_1}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{Y} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} (Y \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial Y})$	(3L)
$\frac{\partial \rho_1}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial p_1}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{1}{Y} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} (Y \frac{\partial \rho_1}{\partial Y})$	(3E)

The solutions involve the modified Bessel functions of the first kind I_0 and I_1 as,

$B = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{\sqrt{sD}} \frac{I_1(\sqrt{sD})}{I_0(\sqrt{sD})}} < 1$	(5B)
$R_1 = P_1$	(5R)
$U_1 = -\frac{1}{s} \left[1 - \frac{I_0(\sqrt{sY})}{I_0(\sqrt{sD})} \right] P_{1x}$	(5U)
$V_1 = \frac{\sqrt{s} I_1(\sqrt{sD})}{B^2 I_0(\sqrt{sD})} \left[\frac{Y}{D} - \frac{I_1(\sqrt{sY})}{I_1(\sqrt{sD})} \right] P_1$	(6V)

where, as for the channel,

$P_1 = Q_1 \cosh\left(\frac{s}{B} x\right) + G_1 \frac{B}{s} \sinh\left(\frac{s}{B} x\right)$	(6P)
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Leaving Region I to Region II or Region III,

$B \sim 1 - \varepsilon \frac{1}{\sqrt{sd}} \dots$	(7B)
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Appendix B

In a passage of diminishing width, the variations of the velocity perturbations U_1 and V_1 with the cross coordinate Y are expressed, respectively, by the cross-variation functions Φ and Ψ given in Table 1 and depicted in Fig. (3).

Table 1: Cross-variation functions of the velocity perturbations U_1 and V_1 for channels and pipes.

Passage	Channel	Pipe
U_1	$\Phi = 1 - \frac{\cosh(\eta)}{\cosh(\delta)}$	$\Phi = 1 - \frac{I_0(\eta)}{I_0(\delta)}$
V_1	$\Psi = \frac{\eta}{\delta} - \frac{\sinh(\eta)}{\sinh(\delta)}$	$\Psi = \frac{\eta}{\delta} - \frac{I_1(\eta)}{I_1(\delta)}$

Here, $\eta = \sqrt{s}Y$, $\delta = \sqrt{s}D$.

(a)

(b)

Fig. (3): Cross-variation functions. (a) $\delta = 5$ (b) $\delta = 50$

Note that in Fig. (3b) the channel and pipe curves are indistinguishable.

It is obvious that, as the passage width increases, a boundary layer forms.